

Musiqiy faoliyatning o'spirinlarning muloqot qobiliyatini rivojlantirishga ta'sirini o'rganish bo'yicha tadqiqotimiz dasturi bir necha bosqichlarning ketma-ket o'tishini o'z ichiga oladi:

1-bosqich-ishtirokchilarni, nazorat va eksperimental guruhni shakllantirish. Diagnostika usullarini tanlash. 2-bosqich-o'smirlarning muloqot qobiliyatini quyidagi usullar bo'yicha tashxislash: V. F. Ryaxovskiy metodologiyasi - Y.Z. Gilbux metodologiyasiga muvofiq muloqot darajasini, "kommunikativ bilimlar testi" belgilaydi. 3 –bosqich natijalarni taqqoslash va tahlil qilish, amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqish.

Maqola yozilayotganda, uchinchi bosqich empirik tadqiqotlar jarayonida har qanday xulosa va xulosalar chiqarish biz uchun erta bo'lib tuyuladi. Shu bilan birga, dastlabki dalillar shuni ko'rsatadiki, musiqiy faoliyat bilan shug'ullanadigan respondentlar orasida nazorat guruhining respondentlari bilan taqqoslaganda, muloqot qobiliyatining yuqori darajada rivojlanish tendentsiyasi kuzatilmoqda.

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THE NOTION AND ROLE OF INTERACTIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Considering the process of learning a foreign language takes place in an area remote from the speech environment, always contributes to a decrease in motivation to learn this language. We believe that one of the effective means of increasing such motivation is to create a personal environment for communicating in a foreign language through a wide use of interactive technologies. The article substantiates the importance of introducing interactive teaching methods in the educational process. The purpose of this article is to demonstrate how it impacts on students' academic achievements. Interactive technology can be very useful in capturing the attention and interest of students, as it allows them to anonymously share their ideas and requires them to react frequently to the material being presented. The use of new methods based on the use of multimedia technologies in teaching English raises the quality of the educational process to a new level.

Keywords: interactive technology; education; motivation; foreign language, role, skill.

Introduction

The education system is constantly being updated. The scientific and technical process is a key factor in changes in the education system, which is impossible to think without information technology. In the world educational program, much attention is paid to the development of standards for interactive technologies in education. Interactive technology has become an integral part of modern society in a short time.

The actuality of studying the problem of using interactive technologies in the process of teaching foreign languages is associated with the social needs of specialists who speak foreign languages at a high level. The use of interactive technologies in the work of a teacher allows students to: contribute to the formation and maintenance of constant motivation to learn a foreign language; increase the intensity of the educational process. [1, p. 182]. By learning a language, a person learns the culture and society of an entire nation. A person quickly feels the culture of native speakers through

sight and hearing. That is, it becomes easier for him to join the ranks of those who have mastered this language [2, p. 34]. Similarly, interaction and communication between professors and students is consistently seen as an important component of learning [3, p. 23]. Since teachers want to see a well-rounded personality in their students, the role of interactive technologies is very important. The same students often participate in class discussions, even if participation is assessed. Additional difficulties are keeping the attention of students and obtaining useful information about the reaction of students to educational material [4, p. 19]. Thus, increasing student interest and contribution to the course is important for professors.

Interactive technology is one of the technological tools that teachers can use to improve communication and interaction in their classrooms [4, p. 36]. As described by Eastman [5, p. 31] thanks to this technology, teachers get instant feedback, and students

get the opportunity to express their thoughts and find out what others in the class think.

The purpose of this article is to develop students' communication in a foreign language using interactive technologies using new programs (Miro's program in the article).

The object of the study is the process of developing students' motivation to learn a foreign language.

The subject of the research is an interactive technology that raises the motivation to learn a foreign language.

Research methods: study and analysis of local, foreign psychological and pedagogical sources; materials from the modern technological world, interactive technology must be introduced into the education system. The role of technology in the process of teaching foreign languages in the educational environment is very high. Many benefits and importance of use: student engagement; improving vocabulary by watching movies with English subtitles; providing convenient educational materials on the Internet; developing independent work skills and confidence in using technology to meet their learning needs. Teachers should view these helpful resources as important assets that contribute significantly to the development of the language.

Kurdziel [6, p. 6] lists five reasons educators use audience response systems:

- To eliminate the limitations of traditional lectures;
- Attract students;
- Provide feedback to both students and teachers;
- Achieve success in learning;
- Improve relationships.

The key advantage of the technology is that it allows both students and teachers to receive instant feedback [7, p. 20]. Professors can ask questions at the beginning of a lesson to determine if students have read the given material, or during a lesson to determine if students have understood a concept, and can also use the technology to conduct course surveys, attendance records, or testing/surveys. Teachers can receive immediate feedback on class performance and determine if additional time is needed on a specific topic. Hoffman and Goodwin [8, p. 422] note the following advantages of interactive technologies: they provide interaction, hold the attention of students, increase participation, facilitate discussion and increase retention.

According to many researchers [9, p. 25], the scope of computer technologies in teaching a foreign

language is unusually wide: they can be effectively used to familiarize students with new educational material, new pronunciation models.

This induces motivation for learning a foreign language. Motivation can be defined as a set of psychological reasons that explain human behavior, its initiation, direction and activity. We can interpret a motive as an inducement to commit a behavioral action, it is a product of a system of human needs and is realized to one degree or another or remains completely unconscious.

There are various motives that determine the prevailing interest in the subject of a foreign language. And all of them are determined by a number of specific factors [10, p. 96]

1. Characteristics of the student (gender, self-esteem, level of intellectual development);
2. Characteristics of the teacher and his pedagogical activity;
3. Feature of the subject. educational resources Miro, Speakout.

Results. Looking at the materials of the collection, consisting of a set of program and regulatory documents of an educational institution, the following characteristic features of teaching a foreign language at the highest level are noted: [11, p. 76]

1. Active interaction of all types of listening (reading, writing, listening, speaking);
2. The use of real, problematic journalistic and literary texts as a source of information that touches on topical issues of our time;
3. Greater initiative and spontaneity of students' speech, which can affect non-standard situations of communication;
4. The main types of dialogical speech should be free conversation, group discussion of the proposed problem, exchange of views, dialogue priority;
5. Compose independently detailed statements based on the text and with sufficient justification for what is read or heard.

Taking into account all these features when teaching a foreign language at a university leads to the establishment of active interaction between students and the teacher, but it must be borne in mind that the use of computer technology can increase this interest. According to the teachers, with their help, you can effectively practice all types of speaking. According to them, the use of interactive technologies in the educational process contributes to the improvement of listening and reading skills. After that, speaking skills continue, and only then writing skills (Fig. 1) [12, p. 184]

Figure 1 - improving the types of speech activity through the use of interactive technologies in the educational process. In foreign language classes, the process of involving students in oral speech on various topics becomes simply boring for the students themselves. Therefore, the activity of their work is sharply reduced, which leads to the loss of students' desire to talk. However, this is excluded when working with the use of interactive technologies in the educational process.

Interactive technologies are a set of methods, tools and techniques used to collect, process, store, present and transmit various data and materials necessary to improve the efficiency of various services. The systematic use of interactive technologies in foreign language lessons allows you to solve a number of tasks in the lesson, for example:

- 1) The formation and improvement of educational skills and abilities with the direct use of Internet materials of different levels of complexity, which allows the student to adapt to himself.
- 2) Improving listening skills based on real audio texts.
- 3) Replenishment of vocabulary with a dictionary of a modern foreign language, improvement of writing skills.
- 4) Improving grammar knowledge with online tests.
- 5) Formation of global thinking skills.
- 6) Introduction of the need to use English for specific purposes of communication.

The results of the lesson, conducted using modern computer technology, indicate the following[13, p. 109-110]:

- 1) the use of interactive technologies in universities contributes to the active and conscious mastery of knowledge of the English language by students;
- 2) computer programs form a positive attitude of students to educational material;

3) the introduction of computer technologies in the educational process makes it possible to strengthen the internal motivation of educational activities;

4) educational and control programs, test programs, arouse students' interest in learning activities, contribute to the formation of logical and creative thinking, and the development of students' abilities.

Forms of teaching using interactive technologies are varieties of lessons. Here, the teacher needs more activity and creativity than with other teaching options. At the same time, when preparing for each specific topic or subject, you can use various forms or combinations of them:

- Seminars are a practical experience from the teacher to the students.
- Interactive webinars are a traditional lecture with discussion, debriefing, slides or films.
- A case is a solution to a specific situation.
- Brainstorming is the joint creation of ideas and the search for non-standard creative solutions.
- Projects are independent work on a task.
- Trainings - a joint search for a solution to the problem, followed by a discussion.
- "Microphone" is the statement of one student on a given question, the rest do not comment.
- Arguments are well-reasoned statements from both sides.
- "Decision Tree" - working with Whatman paper: groups write down the solution to the situation, then change the paper, adding their thoughts to the paper of their neighbors.

In recent years, due to various conditions in the world, distance learning has become increasingly widespread. That is why in our study we looked for new interactive technologies and experimented with teaching English to our students using new programs during distance learning.

As an interactive program, we took the Miro program, which is currently widely used by foreign language teachers. With the help of this program, you can do various exercises aimed at arousing the interest of students. Miro is an interactive whiteboard software developed by Miro.com. Miro is a software company with offices around the world, co-headquartered in Amsterdam and San Francisco. In this interactive program, you can complete exercises that cover all English language learning skills (listening, reading, speaking, writing), as well as create many tasks for students to perform and analyze their speech. The main advantage of the program is that it is up-to-date, which can arouse interest among students. After analyzing the classes conducted in this program, identifying the pros and cons of using

interactive technologies in foreign language lessons, we will share in this article.

First, we selected vocabulary and conversation from the Speakout textbook on the topic "Work and Experience" in a professional English lesson with 1st year students in the profession foreign language: two foreign languages, and since the grammar exercises in this textbook are weak, we chose the Present Perfect part from English textbook. It will be very difficult to teach from two textbooks, because if the students' attention is distracted, it will be difficult to rekindle their interest in the lesson. That's why we first had to find the program. At the moment, the advantage of the Miro program is that you can enter materials from different sources on one board. In the picture below you can see a draft of a general lesson on this topic.

Figure 2. (Interactive lesson on "Job and experience")

First of all, using a brainstorming method, the teacher shows pictures, asks the students what they see, and asks them to think about the topic.

Figure 3. Brainstorming method

Once a topic is defined, text related to the topic will be displayed on the board. Students read the text by scanning and give their thoughts to questions on the text. Definitions will be given so that students can find new words in the text. And students find and compare in the text the word corresponding to this definition.

B Find phrases in the texts which mean:

- 1 new and difficult for you (paragraph 1)
- 2 what happens to you (paragraph 2)
- 3 had spare time (Jasmine21)
- 4 searching carefully (TallThinGuy)
- 5 tried hard to (TallThin Guy)
- 6 continue (Chiek)

Definitions:

- outside your comfort zone
- had more time on my hands
- made much more of an effort
- how you get on
- digging into
- carry on

Figure 4. Matching new word and its definition

A grammatical topic is explained to the students, and sentences are formed by connecting it with a new topic. It also hosts interactive activities. Since the topic is related to experience, it is very effective to use the present perfect tense here. Fig.5

Present Perfect Tense

Study this example situation:

I've lost my key.

I/we/they/you have (= I've etc.)	finished
he/she/it has (= he's etc.)	lost
	done
	been

Study this example conversation:

DAVE: Have you travelled a lot, Jane?
 JANE: Yes, I've been to lots of places.
 DAVE: Really? Have you ever been to China?
 JANE: Yes, I've been to China twice.
 DAVE: What about India?
 JANE: No, I haven't been to India.

When we talk about a period of time that continues from the past until now, we use the present perfect (have been / have travelled etc.). Here, Dave and Jane are talking about the places Jane has visited in her life, which is a period that continues until now.

In the following examples too, the speakers are talking about a period that continues until now (recently / in the last few days / so far / since breakfast etc.):

- Have you heard anything from Brian recently?
- I've met a lot of people in the last few days.
- Everything is going well. We haven't had any problems so far.
- I'm hungry. I haven't eaten anything since breakfast. (= from breakfast until now)
- It's good to see you again. We haven't seen each other for a long time.

Exercise B:

Complete these sentences using the words in brackets. Then check in the texts.

- 1 Choose something you _____ before. (never/do)
- 2 I _____ my first challenge. (just/finish)
- 3 In the last six months I _____ how to sail. (learn)
- 4 I _____ yoga for years. (do)

Exercise C:

Read the situations and write sentences with just, already or yet.

- 1 After lunch you go to see a friend at her house. She says, "Would you like something to eat?" You say: No thank you. I've just had lunch. (have lunch)
- 2 Joe goes out. Five minutes later, the phone rings and the caller says, "Can I speak to Joe?" You say: I'm afraid _____ (go out)
- 3 You are eating in a restaurant. The waiter thinks you have finished and starts to take your plate away. You say: Wait a minute! _____ (not / finish)
- 4 You plan to eat at a restaurant tonight. You phoned to reserve a table. Later your friend says, "Shall I phone to reserve a table?" You say: No, _____ (do it)
- 5 You know that a friend of yours is looking for a place to live. Perhaps she has been successful. Ask her: You say: _____ ? (find)
- 6 You are still thinking about where to go for your holiday. A friend asks, "Where are you going for your holiday?" You say: _____ (not / decide)
- 7 Linda went shopping, but a few minutes ago she returned. Somebody asks, "Is Linda still out shopping?" You say: No, _____ (come back)

Figure 5. Present Perfect Tense

Thanks to student feedback, it was noted that interactive technologies have many advantages. This technology is a very effective way to promote communication.

The results of the lesson, conducted using modern computer technologies, testify to the following: [11., p. 109-110]

- 1) the use of interactive technologies in universities contributes to the active and conscious mastery of knowledge of the English language by students;
- 2) computer programs form a positive attitude of students to educational material;
- 3) the introduction of computer technologies in the educational process makes it possible to strengthen the internal motivation of educational activities;
- 4) educational and control programs, test programs, arouse students' interest in learning activities, contribute to the formation of logical and creative thinking, and the development of students' abilities.

Increasingly, the question arises about the use of the Internet and computer technology in the process of teaching foreign languages in Kazakhstani educational institutions. The distance learning system includes educational material about the language, created by the

teachers of the department. The program includes dialogues, parallel texts, dictionaries to the original and exercises to consolidate the educational material, which are compiled taking into account all stages of learning a foreign language.

Conclusion:

As a result of our research, we came to the conclusion that the use of interactive learning technologies in teaching foreign languages is likely to largely solve the same methodological problems as traditional teaching aids. But in computer education, this is done on a faster basis, because computer technologies have the following capabilities: they have a significant amount of memory and high speed; make it possible not only to distribute educational material and record answers, but also to analyze students' answers and requests, which is very important for independent work; they connect the educational material (computer program) with the student in a dialogue mode, imitating some functions of the teacher and, to some extent, communication; multifactorial statistical collection and analysis of information obtained during computer lessons is carried out in automatic mode, without disturbing the natural course

of a computer lesson. Thus, interactive learning technology helps the student to adjust the tactics of self-education, and the teacher to develop a personal approach to the individual student and to the class as a whole. In addition, interactive learning technologies are currently used, containing a huge cultural and didactic potential around the world. However, for the effective and efficient use of interactive teaching technologies in teaching foreign languages, huge scientific research is required, the results of which make it possible to determine general and particular principles of work, criteria for selecting materials, as well as significantly update the logistics methodology. means and methods of teaching.

Summarizing the above, it can be noted that the use of interactive technology cannot solve all the problems, although it appears in the field of modern education, it affects its quality.

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